

SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE OF THE LEARNING CONTEXT

Ruzmatova Sevara Axmatjanovna
Andijan branch of Kokand University
English language teacher
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The target group of students live and study in Andijan city, Uzbekistan. They learn the English language as a Foreign Language. In the last few decades, the popularity of the English language has increased sharply that indicates a high interest in learning English as a foreign language. All private and public schools follow the national curriculum that aligns with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) that is designed to teach English as a Foreign Language. The government systematically modifies and reforms instructional recourses and assessment system to standardize language proficiency levels across educational institutions both private and public sectors. The government emphasizes the importance of involving more native speakers in educational system while the role of interlocutors should not be underestimated (Kachru, 1990). The reason is that there might be need for educators who use English as additional language to maintain productive learning journey. Many students of the target group are from affluent families and they have to attend specialized schools and educational centers where they conduct English classes that follow the standard language norms with little exposure to any other language varieties. The main requirement for all school students is to achieve international certificates, such as SAT and IELTS in order to be admitted to local and international higher education institutions.

The target local area is a multilingual and multinational country where the Uzbek language is the official language. However, Russian remains widely spoken language in urban areas like capital city and touristic cities. English is gaining popularity among young people in educational settings. On the other hand, the country's language proficiency level remains low. Temirov (2022) claims that Uzbekistan ranks 98th out of 114 countries in the 2024 EF English Proficiency Index (B1 on the CEFR scale). On the governmental level, there have been many programs introduced focusing on improving the proficiency level of Uzbek students. For example, the Agency for Promoting Foreign Language Learning, which is under the Cabinet of Ministers were created by the president of the country. This agency is responsible for developing effective teaching programs and implementing teaching methods in public and private schools. The educators of the English language regularly trained to increase the quality of language lesson delivery. However, school students still need to conduct extra lessons after school to meet the international standard norms in a language proficiency as many of them come from non-English speaking communities. These course does not cost cheap. There are many expanded families with more than 3 children in one family. In these cases, attending extra lessons or tutorials can cost much money which many families cannot afford. This can lead to segregation between families with low socioeconomical background and elites who can afford this. Regarding to the socioeconomic portfolio of the target group, most of the families present all attributes of prestigious and wealthy communities This fact allows most of the students to afford to be educated in western universities. As a result, these students have a very strong intrinsic motivation to learn the language. However, there are 2 students who come from middle class families. These two students study in the school with school scholarship. This fact is nor welcomed by the rest of the students so these students are often criticized for obtaining

scholarship, perfect academic performance, and active participation in school life. In overall, the target classroom represents a multilingual and multinational communities in one classroom. To keep the lessons more engaging and to make the learning process more productive, cultures aspects of these communities should be implemented into curriculum. This action can lead to more close bounds among small ethnic groups. It is emphasized to apply critical pedagogy in planning the materials for these students. As a result, the course instructional recourses are the product of the combination of English-speaking countries culture with the local traditions. The course reading materials does not cover the topics that are not relevant to cultural and ideological aspects of the local context.

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